

IMAGINATION AND MESSAGE

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Abstract

The present study aims to highlight the relationship between the message and the imagination that supports and builds it. For this purpose, it is resorted to the study of an imaginary creation par excellence, such as the lyrical creation. The articulations of a volume of poetry are unraveled and the ways of passing some imaginary elements into the message are recorded. It is concluded that any message has a more or less pronounced imaginary basis and that the correct decoding of any message from this imaginary basis must start.

Keywords: message, imagination, communication, structuring

1. Introduction

Iulian Caragea is a poet of his kind, he has the words and the images; for times against this, nothing can be done. He tried, however, by putting the imaginary to substitute the real and thus remove the veil of self-disenchantment. Thus he imagined in a prose poem ("Winter with Tania", published in "Viata Românească", 3-4, 2012) that in his youth he would have gone to France, crossing the Danube illegally by swimming and, curious, returning the same. On the other hand, to comply with the criterion, the French teacher Iulian Caragea allowed himself to be poeticized as Julien Caragea, the poetic stage name. Paraphrasing from afar the mentioned poem in prose, Iulian Caragea would have caroled his modesty, delicacy and elegance to Baudelaire's homeland and would have returned home with them, to Piscu Vechi, on the Doljului Danube.

2. The initial fact, imaginary fact

Being a poet, Julien Caragea writes with the consciousness of the reality of this poetic, imaginary fact. The fundamental lyrical situation of Julien Caragea's poem is that the concrete self leaves home and returns as another, goes out the reverie door as one, then returns as another. "I am another" says Goliadkin from "The Double" by F. M. Dostoevsky. Or as Arthur Rimbaud says, closer to the soul of the French teacher, in a famous letter to Paul Demeny, dated May 15, 1871, "Car je est un autre". Through the volume of poems "Duminici post-restant" (Bucharest, Publishing Pavcon, 2021), Julien Caragea continues the unfolding of a poetics of

upheaval of words in images from different sections of the living existential; relatedly, the development takes place through two interesting formal procedures, the exile of the title at the end and the putting of the poem on the page in prose format (except for two poems).

The opening poem, a kind of "foreword", is the only one with the title in its place (in two lines, however, "at the front of a bodija/ arranged by the road"), with the verses in their native language, written with various rhythms and in multiple rhymes. The opening in a playful tonality and Arghesian light: "to guard these bubes/ sharp smell of gasoline/ slums and baces". It is a singularity of appearance which does not affect the essence; this poem is in fact just an exercise through which the poetic baggage and lyrical culture are rolled out, since in fact the volume is (to press the keys of the great Romanian lyricist) a Bacovian writing awakened to reality by barbie electric impulses and modulated from time to time by of Luddism and Arghesian assonances. These lyrical lines by which we put the volume in a frame are only to show where this poem flies to us, and not to scrutinize the book or the author.

On the other hand, the one of today is different from the one of the past: "The disease was a great love, appeared in the first youth, Osteoarticular, The ropes of the ship creaked, from all the joints, distinctly, They climbed on them, knives in tusks , the raven sailors, Dutiful, decent reciprocity, of a warm feeling, We were just children back then, Then we knew nothing of each other" ("Inheritance of a, much paler, universe"); "All my ages, collected in a photo taken at the graduation of the cadet school, And caught at home by the slats of the bed, The dead like to pose in song uniforms, Soft childhood, dreaming of scholars and walking in the wheelchair, The image had veiled, myopic , you managed with difficulty to pick the voluptuous fruits from the dark shelves, Our teachers (slags released from the furnaces) were absent (floating somewhere, not far, with unnatural tin wings" ("Grandma's Crinoline colonizing the planet Mars")

The lyrical process therefore takes the real into the imaginary (Ahmad & Farrukh, 2017; Nair, 2021; Marchenko et al., 2022). Sometimes the similitudes of vibration are translated into poems through intertextuality phenomena natural to a cultured poet. Here are some examples: "Crackling from time to time, And their flame groans" ("Piano with a rush of ideas") vs. "Cracking from time to time,/(...)/And their flame moans" "Mama" by George Coşbuc); "Stars in the sky" ("Queue at the passport service") vs. The stars are in the sky" (Mihai Eminescu); "O vino odide mareţ future" ("A small pause for compromise") vs "O vino odide, mareţ future" ("Final Poem", George Bacovia). The one who writes the poem is different from the one who experienced the lyrical event. The lyrical act makes reverie, dreams from the world, from current world events. More the poetic vibration that derives from mundane events is written in other words than in the actual world it registers as reality. A variant of this multiplication of the universes, the levels of the world, is the dream within the dream: "From the dream from the dream and from the real sleep, Father and mother are long dead, the Home has a completely different conformation"

("Octopus"). This state of exit allows the lyrical self to experience what it's like to live after you've died the first time (Faradila; Cagape, 2022; Rahimian et al., 2022), or after those who have gone seem to be around, show themselves in reverie as if they were around. Somehow poetry rises in the edge of the real and in the movement of the imaginary (Mocanu, 2020; Negrea, 2021; Aki & Perkasa, 2022; Kürtül, 2022; Vlad, 2022; Stănescu, 2022). The departure from reality indicates that Julien Caragea is a poet who relies on spontaneity.

Iulian Caragea was a poet of his kind, but he did not take himself seriously until late. He was in no hurry to let Julien Caragea become visible. Even now his lyrical conduct is inscribed under some verses of Baudelaire that tell us that the world is full of mysteries, wonders, delights and fascinations and that it is worth living lives to enjoy it: "Mainte fleur epanche a regret/ Son perfume doux comme un secret/ Dans les solitudes profondes." ("Le guignon" ("So many flowers give in vain/ their subtle and rare perfume/ In secret and in solitude", "Unfortunate", translated by Al. Philippide).

In any case, he unknowingly brought his real self to his being as a poet, training as a French teacher and calling himself Julien. He had the talent, he had the poetic current; he needed a click and that was it. And the old youth and the new youth of now and lived them at home. Julien manifested himself accurately in the literary plane only around 2000. As you can see, the poet Julien Caragea beat his wings a lot to rise. But when he did, his flight was and remained high, cursive, inspired. Write with measured words. When he settles on a lyrical idea, he makes it revealing, exciting, memorable: "What gives resistance to this morning is a dignity, like cement, anchored in the harbor of the small port with a construction site, What gives greatness is the desire to return, not to leave" ("La vie en rose").

The lexicon of Julien Caragea's poetry is vibrant in itself, and when it is selected and drawn into lyrical reverie it acquires exponentially growing power of suggestion. In the air of the lyrical situation, the word catches a multiple imaginary echo; in this echo, he does not demultiply and weaken, he does not wear out, he does not exhaust himself, as in physical reality. Once brought into the poem, the chosen word is strengthened during the run in echo, assonance and inner rhymes: "I was descending held on the chain of the fountain. The rust of the Bible's pride, smooth shepherds of wool, and non-iconoclast, only a talented gymnast, Without vertigo, I immersed myself, soothingly, in the old traditional urgies... And rarely, it seemed, I heard the alpine bells, the slow clink of foreign kitchens" ("Recul"); "The visit again, on a slow horse - a horse with wide eyes (of catapetesma) and bare mounts, like mine, yours -, Dragging in the hulbes towards somewhere, when it was light, scents of vapsea (lazy scents) - the sky purple, honey dew. (It seems a white cuckoo the rare hitch.) And in the smooth stone, equally compromised, under the avenue, (bent glances), with tractor engine earthquake duduie" ("Techno for truck drivers. Windshield wipers mowing the rain"). Written in this way, in such an implicit poetics, Julien Caragea's lyrics seem to project mundane, common events into the

imagination. Its events are interrogations, anxieties, wonders, frowns that leave and, having left, return more nervous.

3. Conclusion

The process of constructing the message makes the real move towards the imaginary (Klyukanov, 2022; Călin; Nicolaiciuc, 2022). What makes any message original is the real from which it starts and the imaginary through which it goes.

REFERENCES

Ahmad, A., & Farrukh, F. (2017). Analyzing Speech Acts In The Pakistani Social Media Scenario: A Gender-Based Comparison. *Pakistan Journal of Gender Studies*, 15(1), 17-44.

Akib, S., & Perkasa, A. W. A. P. (2022). Peran Komunikasi dalam Dunia Pendidikan. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Konseling*, 4(4), 5589-5596.

Basic, G. (2022). Symbolic Interaction, Power, and War: Narratives of Unaccompanied Young Refugees with War Experiences in Institutional Care in Sweden. *Societies*, 12(3), 90.

Cagape, W. G. P. (2022). Centro escolar university graduate school.

Călin, R. A. The fascinating Professor. A point of view. *Psychology-Pedagogy*, 128.

Caragea, J. (2021). Duminici post-restant. București: Editura Pavcon.

Dostoievski, F. M. (2022). Dublul. București: Editura Art.

Draguta, I. (2022). Overview on possible causes of COVID-19. *Moldovan Medical Journal*, 48.

Faradila, N. Language style used in folklore written in senior high school's english textbook.

Gioroceanu, A. (2022). The principle of cooperation as an application of the cooperative principle in some recent rulings of the Court of Justice of the European Union regarding Romania. *Lodz Papers in Pragmatics*, 18(1), 91-112.

Hamida, N., & Nurhajati, L. (2022). Analisis hermeneutika Gadamer pada buku hidup yang digerakkan oleh tujuan karya rick warren. *Scriptura*, 12(1), 13-24.

Klyukanov, I. E. (2022). *Communication: A House Seen from Everywhere* (Vol. 2). Berghahn Books.

Kiselicki, M., Josimovski, S., & Pulevska-Ivanovska, L. (2022). Process of e-recruitment for entry level positions in North Macedonia. *Economic and business trends shaping the future*, 304.

Kürtül, N. (2022). Evaluation of online learning from different aspects. *Theory and Research in Educational Sciences*, 1.

Mara, V. L. A. D. Political, Social and Cultural Implications In The'90s British Music Scene: "The Battle Of Britpop". *Recent Trends In Social Sciences*, 105. https://www.cilconference.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/CIL-2021_varianta-finala_B5.pdf#page=105

Marchenko, T. et al. (2022). The Artistic Modelling of History in the Aesthetic Consciousness of a Time Period as a Methodological Problem of Postmodernism. *Postmodern Openings*, 13(2), 198-212.

Mocanu, A. (2020). Storytelling And Cinematic Strategies In Advertising Spots. *Annals of the University of Craiova for Journalism, Communication and Management*, 6(1), 5-12.

Nair, D. S. (2021). Tracing Counter Memory: An Inquiry into the Mediation of Silence in Empirical Media Coding Practices. *Global Media Journal: Indian Edition*, 13(1).

Negrea, X. (2021). Information and Communication–The Limits of Media Discourse. Case Study–Romanian School in the News. *LUMEN Proceedings*, 17, 492-497.

Nicolaiciuc, N. (2022). Aspecte filosofice ale activității sportive. In *Probleme actuale ale teoriei și practicii culturii fizice* (pp. 33-36).

Orzeacă, M. (2021). Transdisciplinary communication in working groups. *International Journal of Communication Research*, 11(4).

Pramanik, S. (2022). Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set: An Overview. *Transdisciplinarity*, 563-608.

Rahimian, A. et al. (2022). Predicting communication quality in construction projects: A fully-connected deep neural network approach. *Automation in Construction*, 139, 104268.

Stănescu, Georgiana (2022). Ukraine conflict: the challenge of informational war. *Social Sciences and Education Research Review*, 9(1), 146-148.

Student, M. C. A. Feature level rating system using customer reviews and review votes.

Vlad, D. (2022). Literature and Journalism in Julian Barnes' "Letters from London". *Social Sciences and Education Research Review*, 9(1), 184-188.